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Manufacturing Companies in OECD Countries

The number of manufacturing companies in OECD countries grew by an average of 5% between 2005 and 2022. The OECD calculates the number of manufacturing companies in its member countries, covering the period from 2005 to 2022. The data includes micro, small, medium, and large enterprises.

Number of Manufacturing Companies in OECD Countries in 2022. An analysis of the number of manufacturing companies in OECD countries for the year 2022 reveals significant differences among member states. Turkey tops the list with 465,755 manufacturing companies, followed by Italy with 348,889 and France with 248,047. These three countries, all located in Europe, show a strong industrial presence that can be attributed to various historical, economic, and political reasons. Turkey, in particular, has seen significant growth in the manufacturing sector in recent decades due to favorable economic policies and increasing access to international markets. Italy, traditionally a center of excellence for the manufacturing sector, continues to maintain a prominent position despite economic challenges in recent years. The strong presence of highly specialized small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) is a key factor contributing to the high number of manufacturing companies. France, with a significant number of companies, benefits from a diversified industry ranging from aerospace to agribusiness. Poland and Germany, with 240,350 and 205,180 companies respectively, represent two robust industrial economies in Europe. Poland has seen accelerated growth in the manufacturing sector thanks to foreign investments and a relatively low-cost workforce. Germany, known for its engineering excellence and the quality of its products, remains a pillar of European manufacturing. Countries like the Czech Republic and Spain, with 182,959 and 166,771 companies respectively, highlight the central role of the manufacturing sector in their economies. The Czech Republic has become a hub for automotive production and industrial components, while Spain has a diversified manufacturing sector that includes textiles, chemicals, and food industries. Interestingly, even countries with smaller populations, such as Slovakia and the Netherlands, maintain a relatively high number of manufacturing companies, with 84,503 and 83,515 respectively. This indicates high specialization and competitiveness in specific sectors, such as automotive in Slovakia and high technology in the Netherlands. At the lower end of the ranking, we find countries like Luxembourg and Malta, with 746 and 3,008 companies respectively. These numbers reflect the small size of their economies and populations, as well as less industrial diversification. However, countries like Malta have developed specific niches, such as pharmaceutical production and information technology. Analyzing the data as a whole, several key trends emerge. First, the presence of a high number of manufacturing companies is often correlated with larger and more populous economies. However, sectoral specialization and economic policies play a crucial role in determining the number of companies. For example, Slovakia and the Czech Republic have a significantly high number of manufacturing companies relative to their populations due to strong specialization in the automotive

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industry. Another relevant aspect is the geographical distribution of manufacturing companies. Central and Eastern European countries, such as Poland, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Hungary, show a strong manufacturing presence, reflecting a trend of decentralizing industrial production from Western to Eastern Europe. This phenomenon has been facilitated by the enlargement of the European Union and the fiscal and infrastructural incentives offered by these countries to attract foreign investments. The data also indicates that countries with advanced and diversified economies, such as Germany and France, continue to maintain a solid manufacturing base. These countries continuously invest in research and development, technological innovation, and workforce training to maintain their competitiveness in the global manufacturing sector.

Number of Manufacturing Companies in OECD Countries between 2005 and 2022. Among the countries that have seen significant increases, Slovakia leads with extraordinary growth: from 6,030 companies in 2005 to 84,503 in 2022, with an absolute increase of 78,473 companies and a percentage growth of 1301.376%. This exponential growth can be attributed to a combination of foreign investments, government incentives, and a competitive workforce. Ireland also recorded impressive growth, increasing from 3,952 to 18,162 companies, with an absolute increase of 14,210 and a percentage change of 359.565%. This increase is likely due to strong government support for SMEs, favorable tax policies, and the growing attraction of technology and pharmaceutical multinationals. Costa Rica saw an increase of 125.058%, rising from 7,710 to 17,352 companies, followed by the Netherlands with a 99.434% increase, from 41,876 to 83,515 companies. Estonia, with an 88.577% increase, and Lithuania, with a 69.789% increase, also showed robust growth in the number of manufacturing companies. Other Central and Eastern European countries, such as Romania and Poland, recorded significant increases of 42.852% and 33.006% respectively. This reflects a continuing trend of relocating industrial production to countries with lower labor costs and investment-friendly policies. In countries like Slovenia and the Czech Republic, the increase in the number of manufacturing companies was 29.648% and 23.240%, respectively. Austria and Belgium saw more modest increases of 14.655% and 10.866%, respectively, indicating stable but less dynamic growth compared to Eastern European countries. In France, the number of manufacturing companies increased by 7.114%, growing from 231,572 to 248,047 companies. This reflects relative stability in the French manufacturing sector, supported by a diversified industrial base. Among the countries with negative variations, Hungary saw a decrease of 1.760%, from 61,152 to 60,076 companies, while Cyprus recorded a decrease of 2.491%, from 5,138 to 5,010 companies. Denmark and Luxembourg saw declines of 9.414% and 11.716%, respectively. Sweden experienced a significant decrease of 17.482%, from 54,352 to 44,850 companies. The decrease of 20.579% in Portugal, from 86,408 to 68,626 companies, and 23.708% in Spain, from 218,596 to 166,771 companies, reflects the economic difficulties and industrial restructuring faced by these countries in recent years. Italy recorded the most significant decrease in absolute terms, with a loss of 132,924 companies, dropping from 481,813 to 348,889, a percentage change of -27.588%. This decline can be attributed to several factors, including the economic crisis, the relocation of production, and structural challenges faced by the Italian manufacturing sector.

Economic Policies for the Development of Manufacturing Companies in OECD Countries. Economic policies for manufacturing companies in OECD countries vary significantly depending on the specific economic and industrial needs of each country but generally focus on several key aspects to promote competitiveness and sector growth. Firstly, many nations offer tax incentives to manufacturing

companies, such as tax credits for research and development (R&D), tax deductions for investments in new technologies and machinery, and incentives for hiring skilled personnel. For example, Germany is known for its robust system of tax incentives and direct funding for R&D, helping companies innovate and maintain a leadership position in the global industrial sector. Similarly, Ireland has attracted numerous technology and pharmaceutical multinationals thanks to a favorable tax regime and a regulatory environment that facilitates innovation. Another crucial aspect of economic policies is investment in infrastructure. Countries like the Netherlands and Poland have invested heavily in modernizing their transportation and logistics infrastructures, thus facilitating access to international markets and improving supply chain efficiency. Poland, in particular, has benefited from European Union funds to enhance its infrastructure, making the country an attractive hub for production and distribution in Europe. Additionally, many OECD countries are investing in digital infrastructure to support the digital transformation of the manufacturing sector, promoting the adoption of advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and robotics. Workforce training and development are other fundamental pillars of economic policies for the manufacturing sector. In countries like the Czech Republic and Slovakia, where automotive production is a key component of the economy, governments have implemented professional training programs and collaborations with universities to ensure that the workforce is adequately prepared for the sector's needs. These programs often include internships, apprenticeships, and refresher courses for existing workers, aiming to improve technical and managerial skills. Targeted industrial policies are another tool used to support the manufacturing sector. France, for example, has launched several strategic initiatives such as the "Industry of the Future" plan, which aims to modernize the manufacturing sector through digitalization, robotics, and automation. These plans also include financial support and consulting for SMEs, which often face greater difficulties in investing in new technologies compared to large companies. Similarly, Italy has introduced the "Industry 4.0" plan, which provides tax incentives for investments in advanced technologies and support for workforce training. Furthermore, international cooperation and access to global markets are crucial aspects of OECD countries' economic policies. Trade liberalization and participation in regional and global trade agreements, such as the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) or the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP), have facilitated access to foreign markets for manufacturing companies. Countries like Canada and Mexico have benefited from these agreements, which have contributed to stimulating the growth of the manufacturing sector through increased exports and attracting foreign investments. Sustainability is another increasingly important element in economic policies for the manufacturing sector. OECD countries are implementing strict environmental policies to promote sustainable production practices and reduce the industry's environmental impact. For example, Sweden is at the forefront of sustainability policies, with a strong focus on renewable energy and energy efficiency in manufacturing operations. This not only helps reduce carbon emissions but also makes companies more competitive globally, as consumers and business partners are increasingly aware of sustainable practices. Economic policies for the manufacturing sector in OECD countries also include direct financial support. Many countries offer grants, subsidized loans, and loan guarantees to help companies invest in new technologies, expand production capacity, and enter new markets. For example, Japan has a long history of active industrial policies, with strong financial support for manufacturing companies through institutions such as the Japan Bank for International Cooperation (JBIC) and the New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization (NEDO).

Conclusions. The number of manufacturing companies in OECD countries grew by an average of 5% between 2005 and 2022. However, this growth is not uniform across all countries. Some countries

have grown above average, while others have grown below average. Among the countries that have seen significant growth in the number of manufacturing companies are Slovakia with +1301.37%, Ireland with +359.56%, and Costa Rica with +125.05%. However, there are also countries where the number of manufacturing companies has significantly decreased between 2005 and 2022, such as Portugal with -20.57%, Spain with -23.70%, and Italy with -27.58%. Italy experienced the worst losses in terms of the number of manufacturing companies in absolute terms, with a decrease of 133,000 units between 2005 and 2022. In 2022, the distribution of manufacturing companies in the considered OECD countries is as follows: 17.11% of the manufacturing companies are located in Turkey, 12.82% in Italy, 9.11% in France, 8.83% in Poland, and 7.54% in Germany.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Percentage Change in Number of Manufacturing Enterprises (2005-2022) in OECD Countries